

THE IMPACTS OF MIND MAPS TO IMPROVE THE USE OF ENGLISH TENSES OF 7TH GRADERS AT A SECONDARY SCHOOL IN VIETNAM

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Abstract: In the field of English language education, teachers have been seeking new approaches to adapt their methods to the changing demands of learners and the modern learning environment. This study investigates the impacts of Mind map technique on helping students improve their use of English tenses, and students' attitudes toward the use of the technique in grammar lessons. The study followed the quasi-experimental research model, with 60 students participated in the control and experimental groups. Data were collected through two instruments including pretest and posttest, and pre and post questionnaires distributed before and after the research period. The findings suggested that Mind maps can be an effective and enjoyable method to improve English tenses for lower secondary school students. The results help school administrators renovate their policies regarding the use of mind mapping tools. Teachers can recognize the advantageous practicality of using mind mapping techniques to improve their efficiency in teaching. Students in secondary school might use the results to modify their learning preferences. These findings can also be used as references by future researchers to improve their own work.

Key words: English tense, grammar, Mind maps, effectiveness, teaching methods

I. INTRODUCTION

Grammar is an important part of any language. It includes a range of topics that help and support learners of a particular language in understanding sentence structure. In English grammar, tense plays a crucial role in helping students master the four basic skills of English: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. However, many students struggle with understanding and using English tenses. They often find it challenging to form sentences. Cowan (2008) claims that mastering verb forms is one of the most difficult parts for English language learners.

While grammar instruction has remained relatively limited. How to use appropriate teaching methods to achieve an educational goal is a wonder because most students learn English grammar by memorizing mechanically. Mind maps, recognized as a powerful tool for brainstorming and organizing knowledge, can be applied effectively in teaching grammar to secondary school students. According to Tony Buzan (2010), Mind maps are especially helpful for young learners in remembering information. Through the integration of mind maps

into lessons, it is expected that both teachers and students can design more engaging learning activities, while learners become more active and creative in the learning process.

Many previous studies in other countries have also used Mind map, teaching technique to memorize grammar and they also confirmed the high effectiveness of Mind map in helping students improve English skills (Riswanto and Putra, 2012 ; Al-Jarf, 2011; Chen, L.,2023 ; & Thai Thi Thuy 2022). These studies have suggested that mind mapping techniques exert a considerable influence on learners' cognitive development in grammar learning. Although existing studies have acknowledged the positive impact of mind maps, their findings are often based on descriptive accounts or researchers' observations, which may not fully capture the reliability and pedagogical value of this technique in improving learners' mastery of tenses.

In the Vietnamese context, testing and assessment are largely based on multiple-choice formats, which heavily emphasize the use of English tenses. Therefore, the present study seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of mind mapping in enhancing grade-7 students' mastery of English tenses through an experimental approach. The research was carried out at Thach Khoan Secondary School to highlight the practicality and pedagogical potential of mind mapping techniques. Specifically, the study aims to address the following research questions:

Question 1: To what extent does the use of Mind Maps affect the use of students' English tenses?

Question 2: What are the students' attitudes towards the use of Mind Maps to improve their English tenses?

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental design to investigate the effectiveness of mind mapping techniques in enhancing students' mastery of English tenses. The goal was to determine whether mind mapping techniques were really effective in using seventh-graders' use of English tenses. The results of the pre-test and post-test study design of the experimental group were correlated to compare with that of the controlled one. Based on the findings, the researcher came up with final confirmation of whether mind mapping techniques were effective or not in improving the use of English tense of seventh-graders.

The study involved 60 students from the 7th grade at Thach Khoan Secondary School for the school year 2024-2025. The students were divided into two classes 7B, and 7C. The experimental group (class 7B), which has utilized mind mapping techniques in their English lessons, and the control group (class 7C), which has continued with traditional teaching methods. The participants in the study take part over an 8-week period, with selection based on a convenience sampling method.

To collect data for the study, two instruments which were pretest and posttest for both groups and a pre and post questionnaires for the experimental group.

The pretest and posttest had the same format, designed for the purpose of comparing the scores gained by the control and experimental groups before and after the research periods. The content of the pre- and post-tests was randomly selected by the researcher from the English test bank, aligning with the lesson topics from the textbook "I learn smart world 7" that are appropriate for 7th-grade students. The test focused on grammar, and tense structures that students have studied. The 45-minute test consisted of two parts. The first part, multiple choice, included questions with four options. The second part, language in use, required students to use the correct tense form of the verbs in brackets, error identification, rewrite sentences using the specified tense. The total number of questions was 30.

Progress tests: Throughout the intervention period, the researcher conducted progress tests following each grammar lesson. The progress tests with 4 parts include 20 multiple-choice questions to be completed within 15 minutes. These tests were designed to monitor short-term the use of English tenses and were delivered through Mind map technique. The test content was aligned with the grammar points about English tenses found in the 7th-grade English workbook.

The study also used pre- and post-questionnaires for the experimental group to examine changes in students' attitudes toward learning English tenses and their views on the use of mind maps. The pre-questionnaire explored students' perceptions, interests, and difficulties before the intervention, while the post-questionnaire gathered their opinions on interest, attention, and benefits after learning with mind maps.

Data collected from the tests and questionnaires were collected and summarized using Microsoft Excel and illustrated by a system of charts or tables. The pre-test and posttest results of both groups were synthesized. The average scores and score gains were calculated. Then, the figures for both groups were compared to find any significant difference of the test results achieved by the two groups, which might imply the effect of Mind map technique on the improvement of students' listening skills.

III. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Research question 1

3.1.1. Students' results of pre-test

In the pre-test, students were required to complete a grammar-based written task that elicited the use of different English tenses. The purpose of this pre-test was to evaluate their current ability to use English tenses correctly and effectively. The results indicated that the majority of students found it difficult to use English tenses correctly, particularly when shifting between past, present, and future forms. They often made mistakes with verb forms, used the wrong tenses, or formed sentences that were not grammatically correct. In the writing

task, many students did not use the right tenses in their sentences. Some of them used only one tense throughout, even when the situation required a change. This shows that they have not fully understood how to use tenses properly and have not had enough practice using grammar in real communication.

The researcher also recorded the students' results in the pretest to create a bar chart which presents their current situation of English tense use.

Figure 1. The students' overall band score in the pre-test

The provided bar chart makes it evident that the pre-test scores were quite low, mostly falling between 3.0 and 6.0. Up to 60% of the students received a grade of three or four, 30% of students who received marks five and seven. Only 10% of students got a grade of eight or higher. Additionally, the researchers displayed the results of grading the participants in the pre-test through the pie chart below to indicate the existing state of using English tenses among the participants:

Figure 2. Results of grading student's use of English tenses in pre-test

It can be seen from the given pie chart that in the pre-test students achieving Grade A-Excellent account for 0 % and Grade B-Good about 40%. Meanwhile, 47% of students gained Grade C-Satisfactory; 10% got Grade D-Poor; and 3% got Grade F-Failure

3.1.2. Results of tests after each week

To evaluate short-term mastery of English tenses, post-tests were administered at the end of each grammar lesson following instruction through mind mapping techniques.

Grade	Week 2: Progress test 2	Week 3: Progress test 3	Week 4: Progress test 4	Week 5: Progress test 5	Week 6: Progress test 6	Week 7: Progress test 7
	Student	Student	Student	Student	Student	Student
Total	30	30	30	30	30	30
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	3	2	1	1	0	0
5	4	5	4	3	3	2
6	9	7	7	6	6	6
7	8	7	7	8	8	8
8	4	6	6	7	7	8
9	1	3	5	5	6	6
10	0	0	0	0	0	0
Average Grade	6.20	6.63	6.93	7.07	7.23	7.33

Table 1. The progress test’s result in 8 weeks

The table 1 above shows the results of 30 students for progress tests conducted over eight weeks. The first column lists the student numbers, while the subsequent columns represent the percentage of marks obtained by each student in the respective week's progress test.

Comparing the results of Week 2 and Week 3, there is an increase in the average grade from 6.20 to 6.63, indicating that the students have made progress. Similarly, there is a steady increase in the average grade from Week 4 to Week 7, with the highest average grade recorded in Week 7 (7.33). This trend indicates that the students have been improving over time. Comparing the results of Week 2 and Week 7, there is a significant improvement in the average grade from 6.20 to 7.33, indicating that the students have made substantial progress over the eight weeks.

In conclusion, the students have shown improvement in their grades over the eight weeks, although some students have been inconsistent in their performance. The significant improvement in the average grade from Week 2 to Week 7 is a positive sign, indicating that the students have made significant progress over the duration of the program.

3.1.3. Students’ results of post-test

At the conclusion of the intervention, the post-test was given after eight English lessons where the Mind Map technique was used to help students learn and practice English tenses. In this test, students worked in groups to complete grammar exercises and

speaking tasks that required them to use different tenses. Compared to the pre-test, their performance improved clearly.

Most students were able to use tenses more correctly and spoke with more confidence. Their answers were more organized, and they made fewer mistakes in verb forms and sentence structure. Some students who had a lot of difficulty before could now explain tense rules and use them better in both writing and speaking. Their vocabulary also improved, so it was easier for them to share their ideas. The detailed results can be found in the table below:

Grade	Post – test	
	Student	%
Total	30	100%
1	0	0%
2	0	0%
3	0	0%
4	0	0%
5	0	0%
6	6	20%
7	9	30%
8	8	27%
9	7	23%
10	0	0%
Average	7.57	

Table 2. Post - test’s result

The table shows the results of the tests for 30 students. The percentage of correct answers for each student is provided for both tests. Based on Table 3, it can be observed that learning English tenses through Mind map technique has significant importance for 7th-grade students' use of English tenses. Their scores in the post-test were higher, ranging from 6 to 9, compared to lower scores in the pre-test.

The findings were conducted comparing pre-test, progress-test, and post-test tests, which also affected the long-term memory of learners through the increase in the scores of the “Excellent” group in the progress-test and post-test, in which the post-test group of students in this group with scores of 9-10 point increased gradually, equivalent to 23%, the scores of the “Poor” group in the post-test of students had no students achieving this score. Thus, the students’ scores had positive changed compared to the pre-test before the intervention of teaching English tenses using Mind maps.

In conclusion, the data collected from the pre-test revealed that the 7th-grade students at Thach Khoan Secondary School in Phu Tho province had considerable difficulties in using English tenses, with the majority of students performing at an “average” or “below average” level. This suggests that traditional teaching methods and materials may not be effective in

helping students grasp foundational grammar concepts such as tense usage, even after several years of English instruction. These limitations in grammar competence negatively impact students' overall language proficiency, particularly in speaking and writing, which are key components of communicative competence. Inadequate grammar will result in students' lack of confidence to speak and write in the language (Angeli-Carter, 1998).

However, after receiving special treatment with the use of Mind map technique, substantial improvements in students' outcomes were witnessed and students' grammar scores were labeled "good". Data recorded during weekly practice showed remarkable changes in students' using English tenses and revealed through the weekly improvement of English tenses level. Despite different weekly scores, considering the whole process, it could be recognized that students achieved better results in the final time of practice in all weeks.

After using data collection instruments, the researchers could answer two given research questions. First of all, the answer of the first research question "To what extent does the use of Mind Maps affect the use of students' English tenses?" is that the level of using English tenses of the 7th grader was not good in general, they still had problems with grammar, as well as English tenses. Secondly, although they did take part in game activities at schools, English tenses lessons using the Mind maps technique are pretty strange to them.

The comparison of the pre-test and posttest results showed that both groups made some improvement in the posttest scores. However, after the application of Mind maps, students in the experimental group achieved much better results compared to those in the control group who did not receive any treatment. This fact implied that Mind map had positive effects on students' using English tenses. This finding was similar to a number of the previous studies including that of Al Zahrani (2015), Riswanto and Putra (2012), Al-Jarf (2011).

3.2. Research question 2

A survey questionnaire was administered to 30 students from class 7B at Thach Khoan Secondary School with the objective of evaluating learners' attitudes following the implementation of Mind maps! based intervention aimed at the use of English tenses.

3.2.1. Students' attitude to the importance of English tenses

Students' attitudes about English tenses were investigated before using Mind map technique, as reported in their pre-questionnaire. The following is how the data was presented and evaluated. Although the responses to the first question, concerning the significance of English tenses in language learning, differed significantly, the majority of students surveyed agreed that English tenses was important in language learning.

Figure 3. Students' opinion about the importance of English tenses in language acquisition

According to the graph above, 95% of the students believed that English tenses is important or extremely important in language acquisition. Only a small percentage of students (5%) disagreed with the function of English tenses as English tenses was regarded as slightly significant by these students; however, none of the students believed it was not important at all. It means that nearly all students understood the importance of English tenses in teaching and learning a new language.

3.2.2. Students' opinion of using mind maps in learning English tenses

Out of 30 students who participated in the research, 27 students (accounting for 90%) are in agreement with the opinion that Mind maps had positive impacts on their use of English tenses and all students (accounting for 100%) would like their teacher to continue teaching English tenses through the use of Mind map. The following table summarizes their viewpoints:

Benefits of utilizing Mind maps in English tenses learning	Number of students	%
It helps me visualize and remember grammar rules more easily.	26	87%
I can understand the relationships between different tenses.	22	74%
It helps me organize my ideas clearly.	23	77%
I feel more motivated and interested when learning English tenses.	25	83%
It helps me concentrate better in English tenses lessons.	27	90%
It reduces my stress or boredom when studying English tenses.	24	80%

It helps me improve my teamwork and communication skills when working in groups.	16	53%
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Table 3. Students’ opinions about the effectiveness of Mind map in improving their use of English tenses

The table above shows the students’ feedback about the usefulness of Mind map in improving their use of English tenses. It can be clearly seen that 90% of the students considered that the ranking function (leaderboard) in Mind map motivates them to study English tenses; 87% stated that using the technique helped them visualize and remember grammar rules more easily. Following these two benefits of Mind maps, students feel more motivated and interested when learning English tenses (83%), and using the technique reduces students’ anxiety when learning English tenses (80%). Besides, students found that they can organize their ideas clearly (77%), and they can understand the relationships between different tenses (74%). Using Mind maps in use of English tenses also helps students improve their teamwork and communication skills when working in groups (50%).

Regarding the feedback of the students towards the use of Mind map technique during one year of intervention, it is noticeable that the experiences that the participants earned from using this technique were all regarded as positive. Students’ positive feedback on the use of Mind map technique in English tenses teaching to 7th grade students suggests a potentially frequent application of Mind map into the English curriculum for students’ better achievement of academic results as well as their interest and motivation in English learning. The positive change of students’ attitudes towards grammar learning may also result from the fact that students found that Mind map technique had a number of benefits. This technique made learning grammar more enjoyable. Improving the use of English tenses through Mind map technique, therefore, was considered not only a good way to learn English tenses but also a form of entertainment for a number of students and the majority of the students would like to continue learning English tenses through this technique.

IV. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The quasi-experimental study was implemented to find out the effectiveness and informants’ opinions of using mind mapping techniques in teaching and learning at a Secondary School in Phu Tho province. It is concluded that basing on the careful process of the practical implementation of before-and-after research design including the contrastive analysis of the results between the controlled group and experimental group, the findings affirm the beneficial practices of using mind mapping techniques in teaching and learning, especially in improving 7th graders’ use of English tenses in terms of English language teaching.

The affirmative conclusion is made according to the comparison of the results from the post-test English tenses test of the experimental group, who underwent the practical application of mind mapping techniques during their grammar lessons, with that of the

controlled group to contrast the differences. Consequently, the outcomes prove that it is beneficial to apply mind mapping techniques to improve the use of English tenses. In general, secondary school students in Phu Tho province had few difficulties with simple tense forms, such as identifying structures or recognizing signal words. However, they faced problems with more complex uses of English tenses, which required them to analyze, compare, and apply the rules in different contexts, as reflected in the pre-test results. After studying with mind mapping techniques, the students showed noticeable improvement in their use of English tenses, especially in applying tense rules accurately and confidently in both recognition and production tasks.

The study highlights that mind maps can help teachers adopt more innovative methods and assist students in mastering English tenses through collaboration, visualization, and active learning. They not only improve grammar knowledge but also foster confidence, critical thinking, and teamwork. Recommendations suggest that teachers provide clear guidance and encourage group activities, while students actively create and use mind maps to enhance understanding and retention. The findings confirm that mind mapping is a practical and effective tool to integrate into English grammar instruction.

The study on the effectiveness of mind maps in improving seventh graders' use of English at Thach Khoan Secondary School faced several limitations. These included restricted time and scheduling, a small sample size of 30 students per group, and the lack of piloting for the pre- and post-tests, which may have affected validity. In addition, the research only examined the use of English tenses and did not address the impact of mind maps on other language skills.

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